

THE ESSENCE OF ACADEMIC INTEGRITY

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Abstract: The educational environment should be the context for individual and collective human flourishing. One important way in which the learning environment influences this prosperity is by introducing and engaging students in a culture of integrity. Unfortunately, these conditions are rare in Uzbekistan and the problem of dishonesty in education has been around for a long time. Building a culture of honesty in every field of Uzbekistan education system is one of the issue that should be tackled.

Key words: academic integrity, functioning, cheating, support, honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility, courage.

In the recent years students' ethical development, academic fraud presents a pervasive problem, which many people concerned about. Academic integrity is the moral etiquette or ethical policy of academia. The term was coined in the USA by the late Don McCabe, who is considered to be the "grandfather of academic integrity"[1 ,1]

As for historical evolution, honesty in academia has not got very long lasted roots since 18th century. This was controlled mainly by the students and surrounding culture of the era. The honor code pinpointed self-esteem, duty, pride as well as power.[2,13-35] Any actions contributing the uprising or creating of any of these aspects within an individual was the goal. Thus, academic integrity was tied solely to the status and appearance of upstanding character of the individual. Any acts of academic dishonesty performed to keep their good name was seen as an essential means to an end.

Most prominent academic integrity scholars and advocates all over the world such as Tracey Bretag (Australia), Cath Ellis (Australia), Sarah Elaine Eaton (Canada), Thomas Lancaster (UK), Tomáš Foltýnek (Czechia) and Tricia Bertram Gallant (USA) searched the core elements of exemplar academic integrity policy and an effective understanding of academic honesty in higher education context of Australia and the USA. [3,11] The surveys also explored the whole approach of self-plagiarism by scholars and classified as appropriate and inappropriate textual re-use in scholastic publishing. In accordance with the pragmatic experience of the authors in

analyzing researchers' self-plagiarism using both manual identities and electronic detection, a simple model is recommended for determining self-plagiarism by academics. [4,7]

Academic integrity supports the enactment of educational values through behaviors such as the avoidance of plagiarism, [5,12] cheating and contract cheating [6,349-367] as well as the maintenance of academic standards; integrity and rigor in survey and academic publishing.

In the contemporary life a number of instructors, staff, students, and administrators embrace the principles of academic integrity because of knowing the goals of teaching, learning, research, and service can only be accomplished in ethical environments. In spite of the fact that, research centres rarely point out and depict their commitment to the principles of integrity in positive and practical terms. Instead, they tend to address academic integrity by identifying and prohibiting behaviors that run counter to the principles of integrity. By articulating the fundamental values of academic integrity, ICAI attempts to frame academic integrity in ways that are both positive and pragmatic by articulating the fundamental values of academic integrity, ICAI categorizes academic integrity as a commitment to six fundamental values: honesty, trust, fairness, respect, responsibility, and courage. By embracing these fundamental values most instructors, students, staff, and administrators create effective scholarly communities staff by embracing these fundamental values. Without them, the work of teachers, learners, and researchers loses value and credibility. More than merely abstract principles, the fundamental values serve to inform and improve ethical behavior and decision-making capacities which enable academic communities to translate ideals into action.

According to recent three year study of academic motivation and integrity, scientists surveyed over 3,600 students from six economically and ethnically diverse high schools in the northeastern United States. Ninety-five percent of these students reported engaging in at least one form of academic cheating during the past academic year. The most frequently occurring theme represented students' desire to have adults take stronger steps to reduce academic dishonesty. A number of students asserted that their schools should—whether through stricter policy enforcement or more meaningful and effective teaching methods—do more to create a culture of academic integrity.

Research has also presented that curriculum, instruction, and assessment are the vital means to reduce academic dishonesty that intend students toward task mastery goals (i.e., the advancement of one's own understanding and competence) and not simply performance goals (demonstrating competence through high test scores and grades).

Effective and fair and methods for promoting academic integrity have long been considered within secondary education. Yet, there is a widespread notion that departures from integrity are on the rise. [7,2-13] With an advancement of technology in the classroom and the prevalence of online classes, new opportunities for “e-cheating” exist [8,463]

In 2020 and as of this writing, due to the COVID-19 pandemic has caused widespread changes to secondary as well as higher education, resulting in many institutions and schools adopting online learning formats. As the development of fully online courses is expected to continue to expand teaching staff and school administrators are faced with the difficulties of developing methods to adequately assess student learning in an online environment while maintaining academic honesty. [9,1]

In general, academic integrity remains an integral element of education. Not only upholding the reputation of an educational organization and the value and meaning of the degrees it confers, but they also create a shared framework for professional work that is extended beyond the academy are the principle values that constitute academic. Thus, as online studies continue to expand education, we believe that it will have a significant role to have evolving scholarship and discussion regarding the maintenance of academic honesty in the online environment.

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